

Improving Early Childhood Linguistic Intelligence Through Picture Card Media at RA Al-Ihya

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ABSTRACT

This research discusses Improving linguistic intelligence of early childhood by applying picture card media at RA Al-Ihya, Depok. This research is a type of classroom action research that refers to the Kemmis and MC models. Taggart includes four stages, namely (1) planning (2) action (3) observation and (4) reflection. This research consists of 2 cycles, each. The cycle consists of 4 meetings. The data analysis technique used in this research is qualitative and quantitative data analysis. The sample of this study were 15 students of RA Al-Ihya, Depok. The aims of this study were (1) to improve the linguistic intelligence of children aged 5-6 years at RA AL-Ihva, Depok. (2) The results of increasing the linguistic intelligence of children aged 5-6 at RA Al-Ihya, Depok. Data collection techniques in this study used observation sheet instruments, interviews, and documentation. The results of this study stated that there was an increase in children's linguistic intelligence, namely 46% in cycle 1 and in cycle II to 54%. The research findings show that applying pictorial kart media can improve early childhood linguistic intelligence.

Keywords: Linguistic Intelligence, Picture Card Media, Early Childhood

INTRODUCTION

Kindergarten education (TK) is a form of education for the age range of four to six years. Kindergarten education is not mandatory education. However, if we understand more deeply the importance of education from an early age, kindergarten or preschool education is a form of education that is very important for human life in the future. This is in accordance with the expressions of various children's education figures that education at an early age is a very fundamental stage for further development and education. For kindergarten teachers, understanding the nature of education and learning in kindergarten is a very basic demand. Kindergarten education is a form of early childhood education, namely children aged four to six years. Kindergarten education has a very important role. to develop children's personalities and prepare them to enter the next level of education.

Kindergarten education is a bridge between the family environment and the wider community environment, namely elementary schools and other environments. The early childhood phase is a fairly rapid phase to increase intelligence development, especially early childhood linguistic intelligence so that this development process can help children interact (Ananditha, 2017; Novitasari, 2018). Linguistic intelligence is intelligence that includes aspects of language. Linguistic intelligence is intelligence that processes words, the ability to use words effectively both orally and in writing. (Palenkahu, 2018; Ulwivah, 2019). Linguistic intelligence or also called language intelligence is identified with intelligence in processing words, language intelligence is language intelligence which refers to the ability to organize thoughts clearly and use words competently to express a thought. The linguistic learning process is an activity of change in children's development. Linguistic intelligence is an intelligence that is highly valued in the modern world, because everyone tends to judge other people through speaking. Linguistic Intelligence is one of the most important aspects when someone is giving a first impression in language. A person who has high linguistic intelligence will not only show a good and appropriate mastery of language,

but will also be able to tell stories, debate, discuss, interpret things and carry out tasks related to speaking.

Language skills are the main aspect of linguistic intelligence which basically consists of mastery of various language components, such as syntax, semantics, phonics and pragmatics. From things like this, the child's language process has not reached the expected level of development, if this problem does not get a solution, then it is very difficult for the child to get satisfactory results in language skills as expected, so a solution is needed to overcome language problems, to overcome this problem. Researchers will use animated image media as a teaching tool to improve children's linguistic intelligence or language intelligence during the learning process. The large number of media in teaching requires teachers to be selective in choosing the media that will be used in the classroom learning process. The success of choosing the right learning media can be seen from how well the student's learning outcomes are and how they relate to the material. Learning outcomes are things that can be viewed from two different sides.

From the student's side, learning outcomes are a good level of mental development when compared to before studying. This level of mental development is manifested in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. Meanwhile, from the teacher's perspective, learning outcomes are the completion of learning material. A conducive learning process will influence student learning outcomes, as well as learning outcomes can be influenced by students' active learning. Students in the classroom may become inactive, one of which is due to inappropriate choice of learning media. Active learning is very important for students to have during the learning process so that the material is... delivered by the teacher can be absorbed by students to the maximum. It is hoped that student learning activity can be maximized by choosing the right learning media. Based on the problems found in the learning process, teachers are expected to be able to find appropriate solutions to overcome these problems. One of them is by implementing Flash Card cooperative learning media.

RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research is qualitative research with classroom action research. Classroom action research is an examination of learning activities in the form of actions, which are deliberately created and occur in a class together (Arikunto, 2014). This research was located at Kindergarten Al Ihya, RA at Jl. Martadinata IV, Rangkapan Jaya Baru Village, Pancoran Mas District, Depok. 1. Research Subjects The subjects in this research were children aged 5-6 years, 15 children as the recipients of the action, the researcher as the giver of the action. data source. The data source in this research is data obtained through observation techniques on indicators of children's developmental achievements, namely in aspects of language development or linguistic intelligence, especially in the development of expressing language and several indicators of developmental achievements that must be achieved by children aged 5-6 years to improve linguistic intelligence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Description of Research Information

The aim of the research was conducted at RA Al Ihya Depok to determine the increase in linguistic intelligence in early childhood by implementing picture card media in the kindergarten. Data collection in this study used observation sheets that had been prepared by researchers based on the theory of linguistic intelligence indicators for children aged 5-6 years.

Description of Research Findings

The first step taken by researchers in collecting data in the field is to carry out an initial test (Pre-Cycle). This test is carried out to determine the child's score before any action/treatment is carried out. After the test is carried out, the next step is: by giving action/treatment to the child by applying the picture card media adjusted to the Daily Learning Implementation Plan (RPPH). After completion, the author then carried out a final test together with the child (Posttest). Based on the results of research on class B children at RA Al Ihya, final scores were obtained for Pre-Cycle, Cycle I, Cycle II from the results of children's activities, which were obtained from 18 statements with the following assessment criteria: Score 1 if the statement was answered Not Developed (BB), Score 2 if the statement is answered Starting to Develop (MB), Score 3 if the statement is

answered Developing According to Expectations (BSH), Score 4 if the statement is answered Developing Very Well (BSB).

Pre Cycle

Pre-Cycle Planning

Planning is something that is done before the learning process, the things that must be done in the pre-cycle planning stage are as follows:

- a. Formulate the aim of improving the linguistic intelligence of early childhood by applying picture card media to group B children at RA Al Ihya Depok.
- b. Formulate Developmental Achievement Levels (TCP) with the scope of children's linguistic intelligence according to indicators.
- c. Make a Daily Learning Implementation Plan (RPPH) according to the research schedule.
- d. Hold discussions between peers about the problem of children's linguistic intelligence by applying picture card media at RA Al Ihya Depok
- e. Providing tools and materials that support learning.
- f. Prepare assessment tools in the form of child observation and interview formats.

Pre-Cycle Implementation

- a. The play environment is a place of activity prepared by the teacher for children in order to develop all aspects of the child's development, where the teacher prepares the day's learning activities in accordance with the RPPH that has been prepared.
- b. The platform before playing is a place where children communicate with teachers and friends about the goals of the learning process and the rules that have been created and agreed upon together.
- c. The playing platform is where the teacher observes all the activities carried out by the children in the learning process, apart from that the teacher also provides motivation and enthusiasm for the children.
- d. The platform after playing is a place for children to express everything they feel while carrying out the play activities that have taken place.

Observation

In this research, observations focused on activities and children, as well as everything that happened. When using this observation technique, it is equipped with an observation format or blank as a research instrument to see the extent of the child's development level. Pre-Cycle initial score data obtained by researchers in the research on Increasing Early Childhood Linguistic Intelligence by Applying Picture Card Media at RA AL IHYA Depok.

Cycle I

Planning

The researcher carried out cycle planning in relation to preparing a Daily Learning Implementation Plan (RPPH) with the theme of animals and sub-themes of 2-legged animals that will be taught to children, preparing children's worksheets, prepare the necessary supporting tools, and make a child observation sheet.

Implementation/ Action

In cycle I, the material presented was on the theme of animals, sub-theme of 2-legged animals. Implementation of the actions carried out by researchers in cycle I consisted of 3 stages of activity. The following is a description of the implementation and observation of learning activities in cycle I, meeting I using picture card media:

Initial activity

At the start of the lesson, the teacher welcomes the children and tells them to first wash their hands, measure their body temperature and comply with health protocols. The teacher opens the lesson by giving a greeting and the children can answer the greeting then ask the children about the day and date, read learning prayers, short suras, and sing. Teachers attend children by singing and doing circle time. Before starting learning, the teacher first provides motivation and enthusiasm to start learning and informs about the animal theme, sub-theme of 2-legged animals, material and activities that will be carried out today.

Core activities

- a. The teacher explained to the children about the different types of two-legged animals using picture cards (chickens, ducks, geese and penguins).
- b. The teacher directs the children to imitate the sound of a chicken
- c. The teacher instructs the child to connect the picture of the two-legged animal with the correct word.
- d. The teacher invites the children to do a maze/look for a trail to the chicken coop.
- e. The teacher mentions the message of today's activities and asks the children's representatives to mention the activities that have been carried out today.

Closing Activities

At the end of the lesson, researchers and teachers reflected on the results by learning the sub-theme of 2-legged animals. The teacher also gave direction to students to always maintain children's health and personal hygiene. The teacher also asks the children about the activities they have carried out. The teacher closes the lesson by praying and singing. Then say thank you to Allah SWT with the pronunciation Hamdalah. During the first cycle of the first meeting, children were able to interact with the material activities that had been prepared and some children were still confused about answering questions according to the topic.

Observation

In this research, observations focused on activities and children, as well as everything that happened. When using this observation technique, it is equipped with a table to see the results of developments using pictorial media.

Cycle II

Planning

The planning for cycle II carried out by researchers was related to preparing a Daily Learning Implementation Plan (RPPH) with the theme of animals and sub-themes of water animals that would be taught to children, preparing children's worksheets, preparing the necessary supporting tools, and making children's observation sheets. 2) Implementation/Action This cycle discusses material on the animal theme, sub-theme water animals. In cycle II, three activities were carried out, namely as follows:

Implementation/Action

Initial activity

At the start of the lesson, the teacher welcomes the children, tells them to wash their hands, check their body temperature and maintain health protocols. The teacher opens the lesson by giving a greeting and the child can answer the greeting, then the teacher asks the child about the day and date, reads the study prayer, the prayer for love for mom and dad, the chair verse, short surahs, prayers for safety in this world and the hereafter, and sings. Teachers attend children by singing and doing circle time. Before starting the lesson, the teacher first provides motivation and enthusiasm to start the lesson by doing ice breaking and informing about the animal theme.

Core activities

- a. The teacher explains to the children about the various aquatic animals using the media of picture cards (fish, crabs, clams, turtles)
- b. The teacher asked the child "Who created the water animals? What are the characteristics of water animals? How do water animals live?"
- c. Children answer questions and the teacher provides explanations about water animals.
- d. The teacher directs the children to imitate swimming movements.
- e. The teacher invites children to do ice breaking.
- f. The teacher directs the children to play with picture card media by grouping pictures of the same animals where they live.
- g. The teacher directs the children to write the word fish.
- h. The teacher mentions the message of today's activities and asks the children's representatives to mention the activities that have been carried out today.

Closing Activities

At the end of the lesson the researcher and teacher reflected on the results of the lesson with the animal theme and water animal sub-theme. The teacher provides guidance on maintaining physical health, body cleanliness and enthusiasm for learning, then the teacher closes the lesson by praying and singing. During the activities in cycle II, children showed their liking and interest in the picture card media and the activities that had been prepared by the teacher and researchers.

Observation

Based on observations from cycle II, the research analyzed the learning process and efforts to increase children's linguistic intelligence. This analysis was carried out by researchers by discussing, evaluating, learning processes, and looking at existing shortcomings. Apart from that, the research is also guided by the results of observations so that there is an increase in children's linguistic intelligence in a better direction.

CONCLUSION

Based on research that has been conducted, through observation, interviews and documentation techniques, there is an increase in linguistic intelligence in children aged 5-6 years at Al Ihya Depok Kindergarten. Through research that has been carried out in two cycles, each cycle consisting of four meetings, using picture cards or flash cards has been proven to be able to increase the linguistic intelligence of young children at Al Ihya Depok Kindergarten. This can be seen through research results which state that there is an increase in linguistic intelligence in children, namely from 46% in the first cycle to 54% in the second cycle.

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